

Establishing Quadruple Helix Cultural Hubs

Core Framework

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01

In Short

This demonstrator presents the **Quadruple Helix (QH) Cultural Hub** model for cross-sector collaboration and innovation between cultural heritage institutions, creative industries, higher education, and youth. The model was developed, tested, and evaluated through the **EPIC-WE Europe Horizon project** (2023-2026)

What

A QH Cultural Hub is a collaboration model where creative industries, cultural heritage institutions, higher education institutions, and youth 'meet in the middle' to explore, innovate, and experiment with cultural ideas, initiatives, and innovations (such as Cultural Game Jams). EPIC-WE QH Cultural Hubs are participant-driven cross-sector real-world laboratories for developing future cultural practices, imagination, and innovations.

Why

Working together in a QH Cultural Hub enables partners to access and combine diverse forms of knowledge, methods, and perspectives - creating shared opportunities for cultural innovation, deeper forms of participation, as well as more empowered and meaningful citizen and youth engagement to strengthen future practices in culture, research, industry, and society.

How

QH Cultural Hubs are established by implementing the principles, model, and steps found in this demonstrator - bringing together partners from the four helices to organise co-creative activities such as workshops, game jams, or projects for cultural imagination and innovation. Through QH Cultural Hub practices, partners develop and test cultural initiatives that can grow locally and connect to wider cultural ecosystems.

Combined, the QH Cultural Hub core framework provides a research-based, tested, and evaluated model for cross-sector empowered participation and partnerships.

02

What is a Quadruple Helix Cultural Hub?

A Quadruple Helix (QH) Cultural Hub is a *locally anchored co-creative site* where creative industries, cultural heritage organisations, higher education institutions, and youth citizens meet in the middle to explore, experiment with, co-create, and innovate culture.

Developed through the **EPIC-WE project** (*Empowered Participation through Ideating Cultural Worlds and Environments*), the model and framework connect four sectors across real-world environments, including GLAM sites (galleries, libraries, archives, and museums), formal and informal learning environments, public spaces, and creative industry settings. Here, partners meet regularly 'in the middle' to enable an 'epic we', co-creating cultural ideas and initiatives, and innovating culture together.

Instead of working separately in their respective sectors, the four helices join forces to combine their knowledge, methods, practices, and perspectives, as demonstrated in **the project cases**. This creates new approaches to co-creative partnerships through and across research, culture, industry, and public participation.

In **EPIC-WE**, QH Cultural Hubs operate as a combination of Quadruple Helix Innovation Ecosystems and Living Labs: cross-sector, real-life environments where partners co-operate, collaborate, and co-create future practices, and then test them in practice.

In **EPIC-WE**, QH Cultural Hubs were established in Aarhus, Hilversum, and Óbidos within art museums, digital archives, heritage cities, game studios, and universities for youths' cultural imagination and innovation in Cultural Game Jams through the creation of games that engaged with cultural heritage, EU values, and contemporary societal issues.

The goal of establishing a QH Cultural Hub is simple:

To unite across sectors by forming an epic we that meets in the middle to co-create cultural imagination, initiatives, and innovation

Read more
about QH
Cultural Hubs

Core Principles for QH Cultural Hubs

1

Democratise cultural innovation through including citizens and users as core partners in the QH Cultural Hub

2

Form equal and transformative partnerships in cultural innovation

3

Institute meetings in the middle

4

Practice co-creative cultural innovation and transformation for public good(s)

5

Develop real-world, real-life Cultural Hubs

6

Advance empowered participation in culture

1

Democratise cultural innovation through including citizens and users as core partners in the QH Cultural Hub

Quadruple Helix Cultural Hubs start from the premise that cultural innovation should be developed with people, not only for them. Citizens, young people, and cultural users should therefore become core partners in the hub, contributing with their imagination, ideas, experiences, and perspectives to co-shape cultural initiatives and innovations from the outset. Instead of being invited only as audiences or end users, they actively participate as core partners in development and decision-making.

In practice, this means creating processes and spaces where citizens can meaningfully contribute to cultural development. Cultural organisations, universities, and creative industries should take up participatory processes, such as collaborative workshops, co-creation labs, participatory game jams, or democratic design sessions, in which participants collaborate on cultural ideas and projects. By recognising citizens as core partners, knowledge holders and creative contributors, QH Cultural Hubs help to ensure that cultural initiatives and innovations are culturally meaningful, socially relevant, locally grounded, and responsive to real needs and aspirations.

Implications of this principle:

1. **Invite citizens early:** Include youth and community members from the start of cultural innovation processes, not only at the testing stage.
2. **Create participatory formats:** Organise co-creation workshops, cultural labs, or game jams where citizens collaborate with professionals.
3. **Recognise different forms of knowledge:** Approach lived experiences and cultural practices as valuable knowledge forms on the same level as professional and academic expertise.
4. **Share ownership:** Ensure that citizens' contributions influence outcomes and are visible in the final stage of cultural initiatives.

2

Form equal and transformative partnerships in cultural innovation

A Quadruple Helix Cultural Hub unites four distinct knowledge cultures: cultural heritage organisations, creative industries, higher education institutions, and citizens or youth. For collaboration to succeed, these actors must engage as equal partners, with each perspective valued and contributing to the innovation process. Equality in partnership enables diverse knowledges, practices, and experiences to meet and combine in ways that generate new ideas and opportunities.

Building such partnerships requires deliberate and sustained collaboration. Partners should establish shared values and objectives, mutual learning processes, and collaborative structures that enable knowledge exchange between sectors. Cultural institutions offer cultural expertise and public engagement; creative industries bring experimentation and production capabilities; universities contribute methods and critical reflection; and citizens provide lived experiences and cultural insights. Through these interactions, partnerships can evolve into transformative partnerships that form a collective 'we' to shape cultural formats, practices, and initiatives.

Implications of this principle:

1. **Map partners and strengths:** Identify potential collaborators across the four helices and clarify each actor's contribution.
2. **Define shared values and goals:** Develop a common purpose for the hub or project that reflects the interests of all partners.
3. **Create collaborative working structures:** Establish joint meetings, design sessions, or innovation labs where partners work together.
4. **Build trust through joint experimentation:** Start with small collaborative projects that enable partners to learn from one another and develop long-term partnerships.

3

Institute meetings in the middle

Quadruple Helix collaboration works best when partners are willing to step outside their sector and established roles to meet in a shared space for imagination and experimentation. The QH Cultural Hub becomes the place where different sectors meet ‘in the middle’ to create a common ground and collaborative environment where new ideas and initiatives can emerge across sector boundaries.

Meeting in the middle means developing shared vocabularies, working formats, and collaborative practices that encourage exchange and experimentation. Partners may co-host innovation workshops, collaborative cultural labs, or democratic design processes in which researchers, professionals, and citizens work together. These encounters enable partners to jointly explore new perspectives, challenge assumptions, and co-develop cultural initiatives. By creating a space where different worlds meet and mingle, QH Cultural Hubs foster cross-sector dialogue, learning, and innovation.

Implications of this principle:

1. **Create shared spaces for collaboration:** Use tangible spaces within local cultural institutions, creative industries, or higher education environments as meeting points.
2. **Design cross-sector participatory working formats:** Facilitate workshops, design labs, or collaborative residencies that bring different actors together.
3. **Encourage dialogue and exchange:** Make space for partners to share perspectives, practices, and challenges.
4. **Co-develop ideas and initiatives:** Use collaborative, participatory, and democratic methods to transform dialogue into shared imaginations and concrete initiatives.

4

Practice co-creative cultural innovation and transformation for public good(s)

At the heart of the QH Cultural Hub framework is the co-creation practices. Innovation arises when partners collaborate to develop ideas, prototypes, and cultural experiences together. Rather than working in separate sectors, participants jointly explore cultural challenges and opportunities through hands-on experimentation and iterative participatory development.

The practice of co-creation is oriented towards public value and societal good(s). Cultural initiatives and innovations developed within the hub aim to strengthen cultural engagement, support community practices, and contribute to shared cultural futures. By working together across sectors and involving citizens as partners, QH Cultural Hubs can develop future practices and products that are cultural-creative, socially meaningful, and relevant to local contexts.

Implications of this principle:

1. **Identify shared cultural challenges or opportunities:** Explore issues or themes that matter to communities and cultural partners.
2. **Develop ideas collaboratively:** Use participatory and democratic methods to generate and refine cultural initiatives together.
3. **Prototype and experiment:** Test ideas and innovations through small-scale cultural experiments, events, or prototypes.
4. **Reflect and iterate:** Gather and integrate feedback from participants and partners to improve and expand cultural initiatives.

5

Develop real-world, real-life Cultural Hubs

QH Cultural Hubs are not only a conceptual framework; they are real spaces and actual collaborations embedded within local cultural ecosystems. They may be located in museums, cultural centres, universities, libraries, creative industries, or community environments where partners can meet, collaborate, and experiment together.

Working in real-world, real-life contexts enables partners to test ideas in practice and engage directly with communities and cultural audiences. Cultural projects, prototypes, and products can be developed, implemented, and evaluated in the environments where they will ultimately be used.

This practical orientation ensures that cultural innovation remains grounded in local realities, cultural practices, and community needs.

Implications of this principle:

1. **Identify a hub environment:** Choose a cultural site or network where collaboration can take place.
2. **Bring partners into the environment:** Invite actors from all four helices to participate in the real-world real-life activities of the hub.
3. **Initiate collaborative cultural experiments:** Organise events, labs, or projects that test new cultural ideas and innovations in practice.
4. **Embed the hub in local life:** Connect hub activities with local communities, institutions, and cultural initiatives.

6

Advance empowered participation in culture

A central ambition of the QH Cultural Hub is to strengthen empowered participation in cultural life. Participation goes beyond attendance or consultation; it involves enabling people, especially young people and communities, to actively co-shape cultural experiences, narratives, and practices with the sectors.

To achieve this, QH Cultural Hubs should practice processes that support participatory agency, learning, and collaboration. Participants can engage in creative production, co-design cultural initiatives, and contribute to decision-making within cultural projects. Through these processes, citizens not only contribute to innovation but also develop cultural and creative skills, confidence, and a sense of ownership of cultural initiatives and innovations. Empowered participation thus strengthens both cultural imagination and democratic engagement.

Implications of this principle:

1. **Create inclusive participation opportunities:** Ensure that diverse groups can join cultural innovation activities as partners.
2. **Support active roles for participants:** Encourage participants to contribute ideas, co-create cultural content, and shape projects.
3. **Provide cultural learning and mentoring opportunities:** Enable participants to develop skills in cultural-creative production, design, and innovation.
4. **Celebrate and share contributions:** Make participants' work visible and empowering through exhibitions, events, or digital platforms.

04

Why work with Quadruple Helix Cultural Hubs?

Working through a QH Cultural Hub creates value for all four helix partners.

For Cultural Heritage Institutions

- Engage new audiences, and especially youth
- Revitalise cultural heritage through new interactive formats and expressions, such as game-making
- Experiment with digital-creative initiatives such as Cultural Game Jams

For Creative Industries

- Collaborate with cross-sector partners in culture, education, research, and society
- Develop new cultural-creative products and innovations
- Access new cultural knowledge, methods, and audiences

For Higher Education Institutions

- Connect education and research with real-world cultural innovation
- Work across disciplines and sectors to produce new knowledge
- Create meaningful collaboration and impact with sectors and society

For Youth and Citizens

- Become active contributors to the futures of culture, industry, research, and education
- Develop creative, cultural, digital, and collaborative skills
- Participate as partners in cultural imagination, initiatives, and innovation

Across these sectors, QH Cultural Hubs foster cross-sector knowledge exchange, creative experimentation, and new forms of cultural participation. Because different sectors bring different knowledge cultures, methods, and values, collaboration often produces “generative friction” – productive tensions that lead to new insights and innovations.

See the Expert Interviews

Impact of QH Cultural Hubs

QH Cultural Hubs function as **collaborative cross-sector ecosystems** that connect youth citizens, cultural heritage institutions, higher education institutions, and creative industries in shared processes of cultural experimentation and innovation.

The **EPIC-WE Impact Guidebook** shows that activities within these hubs create impact that **travels across sectors**. Rather than remaining within their sector, organisations, participants, learning, ideas, and collaborations circulate throughout the entire ecosystem.

- 1. **Youth citizens develop cultural and creative confidence and acquire new skills**
- ✿ 2. **Cultural institutions explore participatory methods to engage and empower communities**
- ↳ 3. **Universities enhance experiential learning and applied research**
- 4. **Creative industries gain access to innovative perspectives and talent**

The findings further emphasise that the most significant impact emerges from relational change. The collaborative environments created within the hubs enable new forms of interaction between sectors, where youth are recognised as co-creators, professionals mentor future practitioners, and participants work across disciplinary and sectoral boundaries. These relational dynamics nurture trust, empowerment, shared ownership, and new forms of cultural processes and products.

Taken together, the results highlight that QH Cultural Hubs operate as cultural innovation ecosystems. Through cross-sector cooperation, collaboration, and co-creation, they nurture cultural participation, creative practice, and institutional innovation that evolve together.

The QH Cultural Hub Model

The model visualises the Quadruple Helix (QH) Cultural Hub, represented as a common house supported by four pillars. Each pillar represents a key sector in the ecosystem: youth citizens, cultural heritage institutions, higher education institutions, and creative industries.

Like structural pillars in a building, each sector provides essential support by interacting with the rest. The pillars work together to sustain the QH Cultural Hub itself — a shared and dynamic space and environment for collaboration, co-creation, and cultural innovation.

The model highlights that the hub is not owned or supported by any sector alone. Instead, it emerges from the combined strengths, knowledges, practices, and interactions of all four pillars, forming a collaborative and supportive ecosystem in which co-creation, creativity, and cultural innovation can develop when sectors meet in the middle to form an epic we.

Read more
about QH
Cultural Hubs

QH Cultural Hubs are more than meeting points. They are entangled cultural ecologies in which sectors, practices, and perspectives continuously intersect and reshape one another.

Rather than operating as four discrete pillars, the cultural, creative, educational, and civic domains overlap in dynamic ways. Ideas flow across sectors, responses ripple outward from local contexts to connected hubs (as explained in *Connected Cultural Hubs*), and insights gathered in one place reverberate across others.

This interplay produces a dynamic and networked environment: local actions spark cross-hub conversations; parallel experiments invite comparison and adaptation; and multiple interpretations of shared themes coexist, collide, and co-evolve. In this landscape, cultural innovation emerges not from linear processes but from ongoing exchange, generative differences, and the collective imagination cultivated across sites.

05

How to establish a QH Cultural Hub

Step-by-step guide

The EPIC-WE results demonstrate that QH Cultural Hubs can be established through the following steps.

Steps to create a QH Cultural Hub I

Step 1 – Build a cross-sector partnership

The first step is to bring together partners from the four sectors of the Quadruple Helix: youth citizens, cultural heritage institutions, higher education institutions, and creative industries. Establishing this partnership involves identifying organisations and individuals willing to collaborate across sectors and co-create cultural imagination and innovation. The impact assessment of EPIC-WE shows that meaningful change emerges when helix partners join forces and interact, making cross-sector partnership the fundamental foundation for an effective cultural hub.

Step 2 – Establish a local cultural hub

Once partners are connected to form a quadruple helix, the next step is to establish a local collaboration structure or site. This does not necessarily require a new physical space; rather, it involves establishing a coordinated site - physical, digital, or hybrid - where partners can meet, organise activities, and engage participants. The hub serves as the real-world environment where the four sectors meet, interact, and engage in co-creative activities, such as Cultural Game Jams or joint capacity-building.

Steps to create a QH Cultural Hub II

Step 3 – Define shared goals and values

Partners should collaboratively define the goals, principles, and values that guide the hub's work. This involves aligning goals, values, and expectations, as well as mutual understanding regarding participation, collaboration, and the importance of culture and creativity within the hub. The experiences from EPIC-WE emphasise that relational openness, mutual trust and shared ownership are vital for successful collaboration; therefore, creating shared visions and pathways ensures that all partners work towards mutually beneficial and innovative outcomes.

Step 4 – Explore and design co-creative cultural initiatives

With shared goals and pathways in place, partners can design and develop cultural imagination and innovation that foster cross-sector collaboration and engagement. These initiatives should promote cultural experimentation, creativity, and collaborative learning. Cultural Game Jams from EPIC-WE are one example of such initiatives, offering structured yet playful settings where participants from different sectors can practice game-making as culture-making, explore cultural themes, generate new ideas, and create cultural products such as games through and for culture.

Steps to create a QH Cultural Hub III

Step 5 – Prototype and test cultural innovations

The hub becomes a space for exploration and experimentation, where ideas developed through co-creative activities are tested and evaluated. Participants may create interactive storytelling, cultural game prototypes, or other cultural artefacts that interpret heritage and cultural narratives in new ways. EPIC-WE's initiatives and interventions demonstrate that these participatory interactive processes and products support creativity, develop skills, and generate new ideas and innovations across sectors.

Step 6 – Reflect, evaluate, iterate and refine

Finally, partners should take time to reflect on the outcomes of the activities and evaluate the impact and value of the hub's initiatives. This involves collecting feedback, analysing experiences, and identifying lessons learned. Using both narrative, quantitative and qualitative evaluation methods helps capture empowering, relational and experiential changes and effects. The insights gained can then be used to refine activities, strengthen partnerships, and guide the ongoing development of the QH Cultural Hub, its initiatives, and innovations.

Getting Started

Now it's your turn.

A Quadruple Helix Cultural Hub begins with people who are interested and engaged in exploring and experimenting with what happens when different sectors come together. Bring together civic, cultural, educational, and industry partners to experience what meetings in the middle, forming an epic we, and engaging in co-shaping futures in culture might do for you.

You do not need much funding or a complex structure to start. Begin small. Find a few dedicated partners, identify a common cultural theme or challenge, and co-design an initiative or activity that encourages people to engage in cultural imagination, experimentation, or innovation together. Participatory workshops, co-creative cultural labs, or cultural game jams are ideal ways to foster cultural collaboration and quickly generate ideas.

Use these activities as opportunities to test new formats, build relations, and discover unexpected connections and innovations. Pay attention to what energises and brings participants together, what sparks dialogue and new knowledge across sectors, how to sustain the epic we meeting in the middle and what new possibilities emerge when people join forces.

From there, keep moving and iterating. Try new formats, invite new partners, and continue refining your hub initiatives as you learn along the way. Over time, these experiments might grow into a vibrant, empowering ecosystem in which cultural participation, creative exploration, and cross-sectoral collaborative innovation reinforce one another.

The most important step is to begin:

Join forces, establish a space, and begin exploring, creating, testing and innovating together.

Want To Know More?

If you want to dive deeper into the EPIC-WE reports and publications to learn more about what Quadruple Helix Cultural Hubs are, what they could become, and how they operate and create impact, see some of the following.

Report: Quadruple Helix Cultural Innovation. EPIC-WE Quadruple Helix Cultural Ecosystems and Cultural Hubs

Paper: Meeting in the middle: Cultural co-creation, transformative partnerships, and ecosystems for public good

Report: The Impact of CGJs in EPIC-WE

Report: Game-Making Interventions with Youth in Cultural Heritage Institutions

Report: EPIC-WE Impact Guidebook

[EPIC-WE Resource Site](#)

Report: Quadruple Helix Cultural Hubs, Cultural Game Jams, and Games through & for Culture

All EPIC-WE Reports on Zenodo

EPIC-WE